

Event - ANSWER

eventID	eventDate	locality	eventType	decimal Longitude	decimal Latitude	minimum DepthInMetres	maximum DepthInMetres	footprintWKT
BB_2011-02-12-G1	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Site visit	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Transect	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINestring(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T02	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Transect	18.5766	54.4857	6	0.5	LINestring(18.5696 54.4856, 18.5835 54.4859)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q1	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINestring(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q2	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINestring(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q3	2011-02-12	Biscoff Bay	Sample	18.5662	54.5005	4	0.8	LINestring(18.559 54.501, 18.572 54.501)

Occurrence - ANSWER

eventID	occurrenceID	scientificName	occurrenceStatus	basisOfRecord	organism Quantity	organism QuantityType	lifestage
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q1	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q1_Zost	Zostera	present	HumanObservation	30	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q2	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q2_Zost	Zostera	present	HumanObservation	60	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q3	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Q3_Zost	Zostera	present	HumanObservation	85	Percent cover	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Aaurita	Aurelia aurita	present	HumanObservation	10	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Aaurita	Aurelia aurita	present	HumanObservation	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	Clupea harengus	present	HumanObservation	23	Individuals	adult
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	Clupea harengus	present	HumanObservation	14	Individuals	Adult
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	Clupea harengus	present	HumanObservation	3	Individuals	Juvenile
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	Clupea harengus	present	HumanObservation	9	Individuals	juvenile

extendedMeasurementorFact - ANSWER

eventID	occurrenceID	measurement Type	measurement Value	measurement Unit
BB_2011-02-12-G1		Surface water temp	20.1	Degrees celsius
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1		Transect length	30	metres
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1		Transect length	30	metres
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q1	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q1_Zost	% cover	30	percent
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q2	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q2_Zost	% cover	60	Percent
BB_2011-02-12-G1_T1_Q3	BB_2011-02-12-G1_T01_Q3_Zost	% cover	85	percent
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	Life stage	adult	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	Life stage	adult	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	Life stage	juvenile	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	Life stage	juvenile	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Aaurita	10	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Aaurita	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-adult	23	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-adult	14	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T01_Charengus-juv	3	Individuals	
BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02	BB_2011-02-12_G1_T02_Charengus-juv	9	Individuals	